

*Protection of Pay during Pregnancy-related Absence
in the EU: A Comparative Study of Swedish and
German Labour Law*

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Abstract

This essay investigates to what extent the Swedish and German legal frameworks comply with, and effectively implement, EU legal standards on protecting female workers from income loss during pregnancy-related absence. It does so by analysing the implementation of key EU directives—particularly Directive 92/85/EEC on the safety and health of pregnant workers and Article 157 TFEU on equal pay—as well as relevant case law from the Court of Justice of the European Union, including *Gassmayr*, *Pedersen*, *Abdoulaye*, and *McKenna*.

The study finds that while both countries have transposed EU directives into national law, their practical approaches differ significantly. Germany offers stronger legal protection through employer-paid full wage compensation during maternity-related work prohibitions, as regulated under the Maternity Protection Act (*Mutterschutzgesetz*). This system aligns closely with EU case law and ensures that pregnant workers do not experience income loss due to medical or legal restrictions.

Sweden, on the other hand, relies on a gender-neutral welfare model in which compensation is provided through state-funded benefits, such as pregnancy benefit and sickness allowance. Although this system meets the minimum EU requirements, it does not guarantee full income protection, particularly for high-earning women, and may risk indirect gender-based discrimination.

The essay argues that Sweden's flexible and liberal model, while promoting autonomy and equality in parenting, lacks a dedicated maternity protection period and places disproportionate economic risk on women. The analysis concludes that a more balanced system could be achieved by reallocating part of Sweden's parental leave allowance to create a legally protected, fully compensated maternity leave—thereby strengthening compliance with EU law and promoting substantive gender equality.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The principle of equal pay between men and women, is a cornerstone and fundamental element of European Union (EU) labour law. However, its application to pregnancy-related absences remains legally and socially complex. While EU law prohibits sex-based discrimination, pregnancy can result in economic disadvantages that risk reinforcing gender inequality. Pay disparities linked to pregnancy may violate the Equal Treatment Directive and reflect broader societal undervaluation of women's reproductive roles.

Despite harmonised EU legislation, national implementation varies significantly, particularly in distinguishing between wages, benefits, and absence due to pregnancy. This creates a gap between EU legal principles and the lived experiences of pregnant workers.

1.2 Purpose and Research Question

The purpose of this essay is to examine how pregnant workers are protected against income loss during pregnancy-related absence in Sweden and Germany under European Union law. The focus is on the application of this protection to workers who are absent either due to employer-imposed prohibitions arising from workplace health risks or due to pregnancy-related medical conditions that prevent them from working.

The study aims to identify similarities and differences in legal transposition and national jurisprudence, and to assess the extent to which each legal system provides effective protection against pay-related discrimination during pregnancy.

This essay will seek to answer the following research question: To what extent do the Swedish and German legal frameworks comply with, and effectively implement, EU legal standards on protecting female workers against income loss during pregnancy-related absence?

1.3 Methodology

This study applies a comparative legal method, primarily relying on legal doctrinal analysis of EU primary and secondary law, national legislation, and relevant case law. The core legal sources include Article 157 TFEU and Directive 92/85/EEC, as well as national acts such as the Swedish Discrimination Act and Germany's General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) and Maternity Protection Act (*Mutterschutzgesetz*). Case law from the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU), The Swedish Labour Court (*Arbetsdomstolen*), and The German Federal Labour Court (*Bundesarbeitsgericht*), is used to illustrate legal interpretation.

I will apply the comparative approach, as it provides a deeper understanding of the domestic legal system and highlights important aspects of how Sweden interprets and applies EU directives in comparison with other countries. The comparative analysis creates opportunities to formulate *de lege ferenda* proposals in a nuanced way by drawing on the approaches of other legal systems, thereby generating new perspectives.¹ Through the method of *mirroring*, I will examine both similarities and differences between the legal systems.² This approach enables not only analysis but also critique of the domestic legal system, allowing for well-founded conclusions to be drawn regarding the Swedish system and how effectively Sweden complies with EU law in relation to the specific directive in question. This will be done in comparison with a legal system such as Germany's, which shares many similarities with Sweden and operates under relatively comparable conditions for implementing EU directives, as both countries are welfare states with similar legal and institutional frameworks.³

One potential challenge when studying a foreign legal system is identifying the relevant legislation and overcoming possible language barriers.⁴ To minimize the risk of misunderstandings, I will therefore rely on sources available in English or Swedish when examining the German legal system, as I lack knowledge of the German language. Additionally, I have chosen to focus on an EU directive, which facilitates the use of primary sources, since the legal framework is based on EU case law that is accessible in English.

¹ M. Bogdan. *Komparativ rättskunskap*. (Norstedts juridik, 2003), pp. 28-29.

² *Ibid.*, pp. 19-21.

³ Ehrlicher, T & Malm, L.A. *Skillnader i arbetsrätt mellan Tyskland och Sverige*. (Bremen University Press, 2024), p. 13.

⁴ Bogdan. *Komparativ rättskunskap*, pp. 41-43.

1.3.1 The Legal Families

Although both Sweden and Germany belong to the civil law tradition, their legal systems differ in structure, sources of law, and legal culture due to their affiliation with distinct legal families.⁵ Germany is part of the Roman-Germanic legal family, known for its systematic and codified approach to law, while Sweden belongs to the Nordic legal family, which shares civil law roots but has evolved along a more pragmatic and less formal path.⁶

1.3.2 The Legal System of Sweden and Germany

A key difference lies in the degree of codification. The German legal system is founded on a comprehensive and highly structured set of codes, most notably the Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch (BGB), which organizes civil law into a logical and detailed framework. German legal reasoning is characterized by its strong reliance on legal doctrine and scholarly interpretation. In contrast, Sweden does not have a single civil code, instead, it relies on a more fragmented statutory approach, where individual laws govern specific areas such as contract, tort, or family law. Preparatory works play a crucial role in Swedish legal interpretation, reflecting a legal culture that prioritizes legislative intent and practical outcomes.⁷

In terms of legal interpretation and authority of case law, neither country follows the common law doctrine of binding precedent. However, German court decisions, particularly from the Federal Court of Justice and the Federal Constitutional Court, carry substantial authoritative weight and are often integrated into legal reasoning.⁸ The Swedish Supreme Court also exerts influence through its rulings, but Swedish courts generally operate with more interpretive flexibility, guided by context and policy considerations rather than rigid legal theory. The principle of *flexicurity* is central in Swedish labor law and combines flexibility within the labor market with a high degree of social security for the workers.⁹

⁵ Ibid., pp. 76-78.

⁶ Ibid., p. 81.

⁷ T. Ehrlicher & Malm. *Skillnader i arbetsrätt mellan Tyskland och Sverige*, pp. 13-15.

⁸ Bogdan. *Komparativ rättskunskap*, p. 169.

⁹ Ehrlicher & Malm. *Skillnader i arbetsrätt mellan Tyskland och Sverige*, pp. 27.

Both countries maintain career-based judicial systems, but Germany places greater emphasis on systematic legal education and doctrinal analysis, while Sweden favors a pragmatic and consensus-driven legal culture that aligns closely with the values of the Swedish welfare state. Germany's legal culture is more formal and structured, rooted in the principles of legal certainty and consistency.¹⁰

In contrast, Sweden's legal traditions emphasize transparency, social justice, and responsiveness to societal needs. Furthermore, constitutional oversight differs significantly between the two systems. Germany has a strong tradition of constitutional review through the Federal Constitutional Court, which plays a central role in shaping and enforcing constitutional principles.¹¹ Sweden, by contrast, does not have a separate constitutional court, and constitutional review is more limited in practice, with regular courts having the authority to set aside laws that conflict with the constitution, though they do so rarely.¹²

Another important difference is that Germany is based on a male breadwinner model, whereas Sweden emphasizes a dual-breadwinner model. This reflects the fact that women and men in Germany tend to hold more conservative views, while Sweden represents more liberal attitudes.¹³

1.4 Delimitations

The analysis is limited to the legal regulation of equal pay in relation to pregnancy regarding absence from work due to pregnancy related health issues, or prohibition from work because of health risks in the workplace. In this context, broader issues of employment discrimination are excluded. The focus lies on statutory frameworks and does not examine collective agreements or workplace practices. Furthermore, the study excludes a deeper analysis of parental leave and consequences on equality and only discuss these issues on a surface level in the context of pregnant workers.

The essay first outlines the EU legal framework, followed by national implementation in Sweden and Germany. A comparative analysis is then conducted, applying legal doctrine and relevant case law. Finally, conclusions are drawn based on the findings.

¹⁰ Ibid., pp. 168-169.

¹¹ M. Weiss, M. Schmidt & D. Hlava. *Germany*. (Wolters Kluwer, 2023), pp. 22-23.

¹² H. Wenander. Administrative Constitutional Review in Sweden: Between Subordination and Independence. *European Public Law*. (2020): p 990.

¹³ B. Miller, J. Carter, C. MacRae & B. Schulz. A comparative analysis of attitudes towards female and male breadwinners in Germany, Sweden and the United States. *Journal of Gender Studies*. (2021): pp. 2-4.

2. The EU Legal Framework

2.1 Maternity Protection Directive 92/85/EEC

Directive 92/85/EEC, also known as the Pregnant Workers Directive, aims to improve the health and safety of pregnant workers, workers who have recently given birth, and those who are breastfeeding. While its primary purpose is occupational protection, it also includes key provisions that have implications for equal pay and non-discrimination. The directive sets out minimum requirements across EU member states to ensure that women are protected in the workplace during maternity.¹⁴ Key provisions for the aim of this study as its importance to evaluate the effects on incomes losses during pregnancy includes that the directive states a minimum of 14 weeks of maternity leave, with at least 2 weeks being mandatory, either before or after childbirth.¹⁵ While it does not specify the exact amount of financial compensation, it requires that women receive an allowance equivalent to at least the minimum income they would receive if they had to stop working for health-related reasons.¹⁶ The directive includes protection from exposure to hazardous work conditions that may affect the health and safety of the mother or baby. If a pregnant worker is exposed to risks at her workplace, the employer must adapt working conditions, offer alternative work, or if no safe alternative exists, suspend the worker from duties with financial compensation.¹⁷ This prevents income loss due to health-related work restrictions during pregnancy. This directive is part of the EU's broader commitment to gender equality and workplace safety, and member states are allowed to adopt more generous protections at the national level.¹⁸

2.2 Article 157 TFEU

Article 157 TFEU establishes the principle of equal pay for male and female workers for equal work or work of equal value.¹⁹ It is a cornerstone of the EU's legal framework for promoting gender equality in employment and occupation. This article is interpreted broadly by the Court of Justice of

¹⁴ Council Directive 92/85/EEC of 19 October 1992 *on the introduction of measures to encourage improvements in the safety and health at work of pregnant workers and workers who have recently given birth or are breastfeeding* (1992) OJ L348/1.

¹⁵ B. Nyström. *EU och arbetsrätten*. (Norstedts Juridik, 2021), pp. 390-391.

¹⁶ Council Directive 92/85/EEC. Article 11(2)(b) and 11(3).

¹⁷ *Ibid.*, articles 5–6.

¹⁸ *Ibid.*, article 1(3).

¹⁹ *Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union*, article 157, (2012) pp. 54-55.

the European Union (CJEU) to include not only direct pay discrimination, but also other forms of less favorable treatment based on sex, including pregnancy-related discrimination. Although pregnancy itself is a unique condition to women and not directly comparable to the situation of men, the CJEU has consistently ruled that discrimination on grounds of pregnancy constitutes direct discrimination on the basis of sex. In the case involving the Belgian flight attendant (the *Defrenne II case*), the Court of Justice of the European Union established that Article 119 of the Treaty of Rome, now Article 157 TFEU, has both horizontal and vertical direct effect. Vertical direct effect means that an individual can invoke the provision before a national court against the state.²⁰

2.3 Directive 2006/54/EC

Directive 2006/54/EC on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation. This directive consolidates earlier legislation and reinforces the obligation that men and women must receive equal pay for equal work or work of equal value.²¹ Although the directive does not explicitly focus on pregnancy, it offers important protections for pregnant workers through its broader anti-discrimination provisions, where any less favourable treatment of a woman related to pregnancy or maternity leave constitutes direct sex discrimination.²² This means that pregnant employees must not be disadvantaged in terms of salary progression, bonuses, or benefits solely because of their pregnancy. Since maternity leave is not classified as working time, this directive does not explicitly prohibit income loss due to pregnancy-related absence. However, other forms of pay-related discrimination resulting from pregnancy are prohibited.²³ In this way, Directive 2006/54/EC plays a crucial role in safeguarding pregnant workers from income-related discrimination and reinforces the overarching EU commitment to the principle of equal pay.²⁴

²⁰ Nyström. *EU och arbetsrätten*, p. 203.

²¹ *Ibid.*, article 4.

²² *Ibid.*, article 2(2) and Recital 23.

²³ *Ibid.*, article 15 and Recital 25.

²⁴ Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation (recast) (2006).

2.4 EU Case Law

2.4.1 *Gassmayr-case (C-194/08) Austria*

In *Gassmayr*, the CJEU ruled that a pregnant worker who is excluded from night shifts for health and safety reasons must receive her full basic salary, including fixed components, to avoid discrimination under Directive 76/207/EEC (now replaced by Directive 2006/54/EC) and Directive 92/85/EEC. Reducing pay solely due to pregnancy or protective measures constitutes direct sex discrimination. The case confirms that pregnant workers must not suffer financial disadvantages as a result of pregnancy-related restrictions and reinforces the EU's commitment to equal pay and non-discrimination.

The *Gassmayr* ruling thus reinforces the EU's commitment to the principle of equal pay and non-discrimination and serves as a critical legal precedent when evaluating whether national maternity protection systems, provide sufficient financial safeguards for pregnant workers suspended from work due to health risks.²⁵

2.4.2 *Abdoulaye-case (C-218/98) France*

In *Abdoulaye v. Renault*, the European Court of Justice examined whether a lump-sum payment to female workers during maternity leave violated the principle of equal pay under Article 157 TFEU (formerly Article 119 EEC) and Directive 75/117/EEC (now replaced by Directive 2006/54/EC).²⁶ The Court held that such compensation constitutes "pay" under EU law but found no violation, as men and women were not in a comparable situation. The payment was seen as a legitimate measure to offset disadvantages linked to maternity leave.²⁷

This case illustrates that EU law permits enhanced financial protection for women during maternity leave, including the period prior to confinement, without such compensation being considered discriminatory under the principle of equal pay. However, the ruling merely affirms that such compensation is allowed, not that it constitutes a legal right.

²⁵ *Case C-194/08, Gassmayr v Bundesminister für Wissenschaft und Forschung* (2010) EU:C:2010:386.

²⁶ *Case C-218/98, Abdoulaye v Régie Nationale des Usines Renault SA* (1999) EU:C:1999:424.

²⁷ Nyström. *EU och arbetsrätten*, p. 211.

2.4.3 *Pedersen-case (Case C-66/96) Denmark*

In *Pedersen-case*, the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) ruled that it is contrary to Article 157 TFEU (formerly Article 119 EC) and Directive 2006/54/EC (formerly Directive 75/117/EEC) for national legislation to deny full pay to a pregnant worker who is medically unfit for work due to a pregnancy-related illness, when other workers on sick leave would receive full pay.²⁸ This constituted pay-related discrimination on grounds of sex. However, the Court clarified that it is not discriminatory if full pay is denied in cases where a pregnant worker is absent due to minor pregnancy-related complaints or preventive medical advice, provided that there is no actual illness or incapacity to work.

Furthermore, the Court found that Directives 2006/54/EC (formally directive 76/207/EEC) and 92/85/EEC were violated where national law allowed employers to send pregnant workers home without full pay, even when they were fit to work, simply because the employer claimed suitable work could not be offered. This undermined the principle of equal treatment and protection of pregnant workers.²⁹

2.4.4 *McKenna (C-191/03, Ireland)*

In *McKenna v. North Western Health Board*, the CJEU addressed whether reducing a pregnant worker's pay during pregnancy-related sick leave constituted sex discrimination under Article 141 EC (now Article 157 TFEU) and Directive 75/117/EEC. The case involved an Irish public employee who received half pay after exceeding a fixed period of paid sick leave due to pregnancy-related illness.

The Court held that such a reduction does not constitute discrimination if the pregnant worker is treated the same as other workers with non-pregnancy-related illnesses, and as long as the reduced pay is not so low as to undermine the protection of pregnant workers.

The ruling clarifies the limits of equal pay and non-discrimination principles when applied to pregnancy-related illness before maternity leave begins.³⁰

²⁸ *Ibid.*, p. 211.

²⁹ *Case C-66/96, Handels- og Kontorfunktionærernes Forbund i Danmark v Fællesforeningen for Danmarks Brugsforeninger* (1998) EU:C:1998:549.

³⁰ *Case C-191/03, North Western Health Board v McKenna* (2005) EU:C:2005:513.

2.5 Conclusion of Section: What Legal Standards Must National Laws Meet?

The cases of *Gassmayr*, *Abdoulaye*, *Pedersen*, and *McKenna* clarify that national laws must uphold effective financial and legal protection for pregnant workers in line with EU law, including Article 157 TFEU, the Recast Directive (2006/54/EC), and the Pregnant Workers Directive (92/85/EEC).

Gassmayr confirms that pregnant workers removed from certain duties for health reasons must receive their full basic salary, including fixed components, to avoid direct sex discrimination. *Abdoulaye* shows that employers may provide additional maternity-related compensation without violating equal pay rules, as pregnancy creates a non-comparable situation. *Pedersen* establishes that denying full pay for pregnancy-related illness, while granting it for other illnesses, constitutes sex-based pay discrimination. *McKenna* clarifies that national sick-leave rules may reduce pay during pregnancy-related illness only if women are treated equally to men and pay remains adequate to protect their rights.

Together, these cases establish that national laws must not place pregnant workers at an economic disadvantage due to their condition and must ensure both equal treatment and specific protections grounded in the biological realities of pregnancy. However, the cases show significant differences in the level of protection granted during pregnancy-related absence. The cases of *Gassmayr*, *Abdoulaye*, and *Pedersen* demonstrate full income protection for pregnant workers, while *McKenna* only guarantees income at the level of sick pay—even though the absence is due to pregnancy-related symptoms and therefore affects only women.

3. Legal Framework: Sweden

3.1 General Rights to Pay Protection During Pregnancy-Related Absence

Swedish law prescribes that a female employee is entitled to full leave in connection with the birth of her child for a continuous period of at least seven weeks before the expected date of delivery.³¹ If she is not on leave for another reason, two weeks of this maternity leave are mandatory, to be taken either before or after childbirth. This leave is unpaid unless the worker applies for a benefit. A pregnant employee has the right to use her parental allowance (*föräldrapenning*) up to 60 days

³¹ Prop. 1999/2000:87 *Obligatorisk mammaledighet*.

before the expected date of delivery if she wishes to stop working in preparation for childbirth. This allowance generally amounts to approximately 80% of the worker's income, up to a capped level based on the sickness benefit qualifying income (*SGI*). Sweden's decision not to impose any further mandatory maternity leave beyond the two-week minimum required under EU law reflects a broader policy approach based on individual autonomy and gender equality, supported by a flexible parental benefit system aimed at providing maximum choice to pregnant workers. This model aligns with Sweden's liberal attitudes and gender-neutral parental policies.³²

3.1.1 Protection of Pay During Absence Due to Pregnancy-Related Medical Conditions

Income protection for pregnant workers absent due to pregnancy-related medical conditions is primarily provided through the sick leave system, as regulated by the Social Insurance Code (*Socialförsäkringsbalken* 2010:110), and complemented by employment protections under the Work Environment Act (*Arbetsmiljölagen* 1997:1160) and the Discrimination Act (*Diskrimineringslagen* 2008:567). Pregnant workers who are medically unfit for work due to pregnancy-related conditions are entitled to sick pay from their employer for the first 14 days, in accordance with Chapter 27 of the Social Insurance Code, followed by sickness benefit from the Swedish Social Insurance Agency (*Försäkringskassan*) starting on day 15. This benefit generally amounts to approximately 80% of the worker's income, up to a capped level based on the sickness benefit qualifying income (*SGI*).³³

3.1.2 Protection of Pay During Absence Due to Employer-Imposed Prohibitions

Pregnancy allowance (*graviditetspenning*) may be granted when a pregnant worker is unable to continue her duties due to physical strain or health risks, as assessed by a medical professional. If the nature of the work poses a risk to the health of the pregnant worker or the fetus, the Work Environment Act (Chapter 3, Section 2a) obligates the employer to adjust the working conditions or reassign the employee.³⁴ In such cases, the employee is not entitled to continued salary from the employer. Instead, she may apply for pregnancy allowance under Chapter 10 of the Social Insurance Code. This benefit is administered by the Swedish Social Insurance Agency and compensates approximately 80% of the worker's income, up to a capped level. In cases of physical strain,

³² Adlercreutz, A & Nyström, B. *Sweden*. (Wolters Kluwer, 2023), p.118.

³³ *Ibid.*, pp. 114-115.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, p. 116.

pregnancy allowance can be granted from the 60th day up to the 11th day prior to the expected date of childbirth. After this point, the employee must apply for parental allowance in advance in order to receive continued compensation. If the employee is prohibited from working due to health risks, pregnancy allowance may be granted from the day the prohibition takes effect.³⁵

3.2 Relevant Case Law

3.2.1 *AD 2009 nr 15*

In this case, the Swedish Labour Court assessed whether an employer had violated the Equality Act (1991:433) (now replaced by *Diskrimineringslagen* 2008:567) and the Parental Leave Act (*föräldraledighetslagen* 1995:584) by treating a pregnant employee less favourably during pregnancy-related absence. The employer did not pay salary supplements that were normally granted during sickness while the employee received pregnancy allowance, and also ceased paying occupational pension premiums during her parental leave. It found that, under Swedish law and the Equal Treatment Directive (76/207/EEC) and Maternity Directive (92/85/EEC), differential treatment based on pregnancy or maternity may amount to direct discrimination. However, the Court ruled that the employer's actions did not breach national or EU law, as pregnancy benefit replaces salary and pension contributions were not mandatory. The ruling illustrates the limitations of Swedish law in ensuring full income protection for pregnant workers absent due to maternity-related reasons.³⁶

3.2.2 *Pending case, Swedish teachers' Union Takes Pregnancy Pay Dispute to Court*

During the COVID-19 pandemic, many pregnant teachers in Sweden were prohibited from working due to health risks, resulting in a significant loss of income as they received pregnancy benefit instead of full salary. The Swedish Teachers' Union (*Sveriges Lärare*) is now suing municipalities in the Labour Court, arguing that affected employees are entitled to full basic pay under the EU Pregnant Workers Directive (92/85/EEC) and relevant CJEU case law, including *Gassmayr* (C-194/08). In *Gassmayr*, the Court held that pregnant workers removed from duties for health reasons must receive full basic salary to avoid direct sex discrimination. The union claims that the Swedish system fails to provide adequate income protection and may amount to gender

³⁵ Ibid., p. 118.

³⁶ *AD 2009 nr 15*.

discrimination, especially when employers fail to conduct individual risk assessments. They argue that EU law requires compensation at a level that maintains the directive's protective purpose, which pregnancy benefit alone does not ensure. At the time of writing, the case remains pending and raises important questions regarding Sweden's compliance with EU law, particularly the Pregnant Workers Directive (92/85/EEC).³⁷

3.3 Sweden's Conformity With EU Law

In *Abdoulaye* (C-218/98), the Court allowed additional pay for women on maternity leave to compensate for professional disadvantages. Sweden does not provide additional maternity-related compensation but maintains gender-neutral parental benefits, which may not fully reflect this allowance. In *Pedersen* (C-66/96), the CJEU ruled that pregnant workers must receive the same pay during pregnancy-related illness as for other illnesses. Swedish legislation complies with this verdict, offering sickness benefit on equal terms, though not full wage. Swedish legislation does not fully align with the ruling in the *Gassmayr* case (C-194/08), where the CJEU held that pregnant workers suspended from night work must receive full salary, including fixed allowances.

The Swedish model relies on partial compensation through social insurance rather than full employer-paid wages. As stated in the ruling of the *McKenna* case (C-191/03), this does not violate EU law in the case of discrimination and is not a violation in this sense. While Sweden offers substantial income protection, it does not guarantee full pay during pregnancy-related absence, which may pose challenges in fully meeting the EU standard of non-discrimination under Article 157 TFEU and the Pregnant Workers Directive (92/85/EEC).

4. Legal Framework: Germany

4.1 General Rights to Pay Protection During Pregnancy-Related Absence

Pregnant women are not obligated to work in the six weeks before the expected date of birth, a right that is protected by Maternity Protection act. This rule is voluntary, and the female worker can

³⁷ Elsa, P. Facket går till AD - kräver full lön för avstängda lärare. *Dagens arena*. (23/4 2023).

continue to work if she explicitly declare a willingness to do so.³⁸ German pregnant workers are entitled to maternity allowance (*Mutterschaftsgeld*), which generally covers the full net wage for this six weeks before and eight weeks after childbirth. The benefit is financed jointly by the employer and the public health insurance system. Under Sections 18 and 20 MuSchG, employers who regularly employ more than thirty employees are reimbursed for these payments, in order to reduce disincentives to employing women.³⁹

4.1.1 Protection of Pay During Absence Due to Pregnancy-Related Medical Conditions

In Germany, pregnant workers who are medically unfit for work due to pregnancy-related health conditions are protected under the general sick leave framework. According to the German Civil Code and the Continued Remuneration Act (*Entgeltfortzahlungsgesetz*, EFZG), they are entitled to continued payment of full wages by the employer for up to six weeks during any certified period of illness, including pregnancy-related illness. After this period, workers may receive sickness benefits from their health insurance, typically at about 70% of gross income, up to a statutory cap.⁴⁰

4.1.2 Protection of Pay During Absence Due to Employer-Imposed Prohibitions

According to the Maternity Protection Act, pregnant women are not permitted to perform work under special conditions that may pose health risks to the woman or the unborn child. Employers are obligated to continue paying remuneration during such periods of work prohibition, as regulated in Section 18 MuSchG. Under the Maternity Protection Act, if a pregnant employee is prohibited from working, she is entitled to full wage compensation, known as maternity allowance. This payment is made directly by the employer and must reflect the average earnings of the worker prior to the restriction, including regular bonuses and allowances.⁴¹

³⁸ Linemann, S. Von Steinau-Steinrück, R. & Mengel, A. *Employment Labor Law in Germany*. Fourth edition. (C.H Beck, 2016), p. 31.

³⁹ Weiss, Schmidt & Hlava. *Germany*, p. 124.

⁴⁰ Kirchner, J. Kremp, P.R & Magotsch, M. *Key Aspects of German Employment and Labour Law*. (Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 2010), p. 12.

⁴¹ Kirchner, Kremp & Magotsch. *Key Aspects of German Employment and Labour Law*, p. 161.

4.2 Relevant Case Law

4.2.1 BAG, 9 October 2002 – 5 AZR 443/01

In this case, the German Federal Labour Court (*Bundesarbeitsgericht*) addressed whether a pregnant employee is entitled to full wage compensation (*Mutterschutzlohn*) during a medically certified employment prohibition issued under § 3(1) of the German Maternity Protection Act (*Mutterschutzgesetz*, MuSchG). The plaintiff had been prohibited from continuing her work due to pregnancy-related risks, and the employer argued that no wages were owed since the employee was not performing her duties.

The court ruled in favour of the employee, confirming that under § 11 MuSchG, pregnant workers subject to a valid employment ban are entitled to full wage compensation. The ruling emphasized that such compensation is not contingent on actual work performed but exists to protect the income of pregnant workers who are barred from working for medical or legal reasons.⁴²

Although the case does not directly cite EU law, its interpretation aligns with Directive the Pregnant Workers Directive (92/85/EEC), which requires Member States to implement measures that safeguard the health and economic security of pregnant workers. The decision affirms that wage protection under German law goes beyond minimum EU standards by providing employer-paid full salary during such periods, thereby preventing income loss due to pregnancy-related employment bans.

4.3 Germany's Conformity With EU law

Germany fully complies with the requirements set out in *Gassmayr* (C-194/08), providing full wage compensation (*Mutterschutzlohn*) under §11 of the Maternity Protection Act when pregnant workers are prohibited from working for health or safety reasons. In line with *Abdoulaye* (C-218/98), German law allows additional financial benefits for maternity leave without breaching equal pay rules, as they are viewed as compensation for biological disadvantages. Following *Pedersen* (C-66/96), Germany ensures equal treatment by providing full employer-paid wages for pregnancy-related illness for up to six weeks under the Continued Remuneration Act. In *McKenna* (C-191/03), the CJEU emphasized that reduced income due to pregnancy-related absences may constitute

⁴² Bundesarbeitsgericht, *Judgment of 9 October 2002 – 5 AZR 443/01*.

discrimination. Germany's approach, offering full wage replacement during employer-imposed restrictions, aligns well with this principle, minimizing the risk of income loss and discrimination.

5. Comparative Analysis

5.1 Limitations in the Judgments of the CJEU in Pay Protection Due to Pregnancy-Related Medical Conditions

The legal landscape surrounding the right to full pay for pregnant workers absent due to pregnancy-related illnesses, as opposed to suspension, reveals a tension between the principle of equal treatment of illnesses and the prohibition of discrimination based on pregnancy. While the CJEU in *McKenna* (C-191/03) established that paying sickness benefit for pregnancy-related illness is not inherently discriminatory if applied equally to other illnesses, this can still lead to income loss for pregnant women who would otherwise be fit to work were it not for their pregnancy. The case of *Gassmayr* (C-194/08) highlight the principle that women should not suffer economic detriment specifically due to their pregnancy. *Abdoulaye* (C-218/98) further underscores the need to compensate women for disadvantages arising from pregnancy and maternity. Therefore, even though treating pregnancy-related illness as other illness for sickness benefit purposes was deemed acceptable under certain conditions, the underlying principle of EU law is that pregnant women should not face financial penalties uniquely due to their condition. The practical reality of income loss when only sickness benefit is provided for pregnancy-related absences remains a key concern in fully achieving the EU standard of non-discrimination as outlined in Article 157 TFEU and the Pregnant Workers Directive (92/85/EEC). National legislation and collective agreements often play a crucial role in supplementing sickness benefits to mitigate this income loss.

5.2 Swedish and German Approaches to Income Protection During Pregnancy

The aim of this essay, is to answer the research question: To what extent do the Swedish and German legal frameworks comply with, and effectively implement, EU legal standards on protecting female workers against income loss during pregnancy-related absence? I found that both Sweden and Germany recognise pregnancy as a protected ground and have incorporated the relevant EU directives into national law, yet they differ in the degree of compliance and

effectiveness. Sweden's approach is rooted in universal, gender-neutral welfare model. Income protection during pregnancy-related medical absence is provided through sick pay from the employer for 14 days, followed by sickness benefit thereafter, capped at a defined income level. In cases of employer-imposed work prohibition, pregnancy benefit may be granted, also at approximately 80% of income, for up to 50 days before childbirth. While this system ensures baseline income protection, it does not guarantee full wage replacement, particularly for high earners affected by benefit ceilings.

In light of *Gassmayr*, which required full salary, including fixed components, during protective suspension, Sweden's system may fall short. This is further highlighted by the pending case brought by the Swedish Teachers' Union, where teachers who were suspended during the pandemic due to pregnancy-related health risks experienced substantial income loss. Sweden's reliance on state-funded benefits rather than employer-paid wages, may therefore not fully align with EU requirements for effective income maintenance and non-discrimination.

Germany's framework provides more robust protection. Under the Maternity Protection Act, pregnant workers subject to medical or legal work prohibitions are entitled to full wage compensation, paid by the employer under § 11 MuSchG. This includes all fixed salary components and ensures no income loss during periods of restricted work due to pregnancy. Additionally, in cases of pregnancy-related illness, Germany offers six weeks of full salary under the Continued Remuneration Act. The Federal Labour Court confirmed in *5 AZR 443/01 (2002)* that a pregnant worker must receive full pay during employment prohibitions, reinforcing strong alignment with *Gassmayr*, *Pedersen*, and *McKenna*. Germany's model thus ensures both formal and practical compliance with EU legal standards, minimizing the risk of economic disadvantage or indirect discrimination.

In Sweden, it is possible to use parental allowance up to 60 days before the expected date of childbirth, and the total amount of parental benefits is generally higher than in Germany. However, Germany offers a dedicated protection for women through the Maternity Protection Act, by guaranteeing full wage compensation during the final stage of pregnancy—a period when many women need to be relieved from work in order to prepare for childbirth and because working in late pregnancy, regardless of the type of work, can be demanding.

It could be argued that the Swedish system is generous and flexible, allowing families to freely redistribute income to compensate for potential losses—an approach well aligned with Sweden's

liberal social values. However, this model is problematic, as it places women in a position of economic dependency on their partners and fails to guarantee protection against income loss during pregnancy. Moreover, it offers no equivalent protection for single mothers, who cannot rely on a partner for financial compensation.

While Sweden aims to promote gender equality, this approach—where the need for specific protection related to pregnancy is not explicitly recognised in the law and where full wage replacement is not guaranteed—illustrates how flexible legislation, though well-intended, can ultimately become counterproductive to its goals.

In my opinion, a more balanced system would involve reallocating part of the parental leave allowance to establish a dedicated maternity protection period, similar to the German model, which ensures full wage compensation and legally protected leave specifically linked to pregnancy and childbirth. Such a reform would not only strengthen women's rights and health protections, but also support a more equal division of parental leave by making it more reasonable to split the leave equally than under the current system—placing any income loss during parental leave on both parents—thereby promoting substantive gender equality.

6. Conclusion

Germany's system provides a higher degree of conformity with EU law by ensuring full wage replacement directly through the employer in cases of pregnancy-related absence. Sweden, while meeting the minimum requirements through public benefits, may not effectively implement the level of income protection intended under EU law, particularly in light of CJEU case law. The Swedish model's reliance on capped social insurance benefits results in only partial protection, which can lead to gender-based income disparities—a concern at the heart of both *Gassmayr* and *McKenna*. In contrast, Germany's employer-based wage compensation system offers stronger legal safeguards and serves as a closer example of effective implementation of EU pregnancy protection directives.

6.1 Final Reflections and Suggestion for Further Research

An important contextual difference is that Germany operates within a male breadwinner model, whereas Sweden emphasizes a dual-breadwinner model. Social attitudes also differ: people in Germany tend to hold more conservative views, while Sweden reflects more liberal perspectives. These societal beliefs may influence how each country implements and interprets EU directives concerning equal pay and the protection of pregnant workers and new mothers—particularly in terms of recognising biological differences between genders, and possibly therefore, the willingness to compensate for them.

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